

Formal Verification of PKCS#1 Signature Parser using Frama-C

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Abstract. Message parsing represents a complex security-critical problem. It has been demonstrated by numerous real-world exploits on parsers, e.g. on PKCS#1 (Public-Key Cryptography Standard) v1.5 signature, X.509 certificate chain, or infamously on a TLS extension during the Heartbleed attack. In this case study, we perform formal verification of a PKCS#1 v1.5 signature parser using Frama-C, where the verification of the parser is realized for the first time directly over the actual implementation in C. This brings highest guarantees of security and functional properties, while leaving developers the flexibility to adapt the code to the project’s specific requirements. We present the proven properties, our verification approach and results. In particular, this work rules out applications of any variants of Bleichenbacher’s signature forgery and ensures that we are able to detect potential parser incompatibilities. This work opens the door to future extensions to other protocols, for example, for parsing DER ASN.1 encoding of X.509 certificates and CRLs.

Keywords: deductive verification, security properties, PKCS#1 signature parser, Frama-C

1 Introduction

As increasingly many aspects of public and private life are digitalized and moved into cyberspace, digital security becomes a major concern. The persistence of some families of bugs shows that code review and testing are not sufficient to reliably clean up the code even from publicly known vulnerabilities. One of the most risky attack vectors is related to the *message parsing problem*. Indeed, parsers are very often involved in processing of input data on external interfaces, where attackers have some level of control. Hence, parsers must apply a *rigorous defensive approach* and provide a high assurance that any malicious input is detected. It motivates the application of formal verification, capable to provide strong security guarantees.

An example of a long-lasting parsing problem—PKCS#1 v1.5 signature forging—was originally described by Bleichenbacher [26] in 2006, while exploitable variants have been reported in popular open-source libraries in 2021, 15 years later [50]! This case study paper addresses this problem.

Goals and approach. Our main goal is to demonstrate that it is achievable to perform formal verification of a PKCS#1 v1.5 signature parser [41] directly on the parser’s C code. We formally specify *functional and security properties* of the parser and prove them in the Frama-C verification platform [5, 35]. These properties exclude any variant of Bleichenbacher attack or unauthorized memory access. Next to that, they ensure *parser compatibility* (with small limitations, discussed later in Sect. 5), i.e., the guarantee that correctly formatted messages are not refused by the parser. To illustrate that, we provide several buggy variants of the parser, for which—as expected—the proof with our specification fails.

Applying formal verification directly on the C implementation bridges the gap between a—typically, more abstract—formal model and the concrete code of the parser executed in practice, thus avoiding any non-trusted or laborious steps (such as code generation or refinement). In addition, it brings further practical advantages. For example, the code can be iteratively optimized or customized, as long as it is proved that each new modification retains all necessary properties and thus does not introduce vulnerabilities. Further discussion about pros and cons of deductive verification on the source code level can be found in [21].

We select PKCS#1 v1.5 signature as a good representative of the TLV (Tag-Length-Value triple) tree structure, frequently used in parsers. In a TLV, the tag field defines the type of the data, and its length field defines the size of its value field. The PKCS#1 v1.5 signature has a non-trivial complexity yet is simple enough to tackle all methodological questions of parser verification. For the same reason, we develop a representative PKCS#1 v1.5 parser in C, for which we perform the proof, while keeping in mind the need of extension to other TLV-based protocols. This parser is capable to parse the message structure specified in [41] almost completely (it is not compliant only to the fact that the NULL field can be *optional*). The annotated code of the verified parser and its buggy variants are available in a companion artifact¹.

Contributions. This verification case study presents the following contributions:

- a formal specification and proof—directly over the C code—of security and functional properties for a representative PKCS#1 v1.5 signature parser;
- an illustration by examples that the proposed specification rules out various variants of Bleichenbacher signature forgery [26] and ensures compatibility;
- a verification methodology based on the definition of inductive predicates, capable to conveniently express complex relations between particular TLVs;
- an innovative usage of *ghost code* (see Sect. 2) to specify the TLV structure and the application of cryptographic operations on concrete input data;
- a report of verification effort, results, faced difficulties and used workarounds.

Outline. Section 2 introduces Frama-C and the ACSL specification language ACSL. Section 3 presents some parser attacks and expected security and compatibility properties. Section 4 details PKCS#1 v1.5 signature and known attacks. Section 5 describes our verification approach and proven properties. Sect. 6 provides a proof report. Finally, Sect. 7 presents related work and a conclusion.

¹ currently as supplementary material for the reviewers’ convenience, see Appendix.

2 Frama-C Verification Framework

Frama-C [5, 35] is a state-of-the-art modular verification framework for C code developed and maintained by CEA List. Its modular structure allows application and collaboration of various analyzers—implemented as plugins—and eases the introduction of new ones. This combination of plugins offers a large variety of verification and analysis approaches. In our work we use the WP and RTE plugins, which perform, resp., *deductive verification* (based on *weakest precondition calculus*) and generation of annotations whose validity implies the absence of *runtime errors*.

Deductive verification with WP is conducted in a modular way: each C function is proved to respect its function contract (and additional annotations in the function body), specified in ACSL (ANSI/ISO C Specification Language [4]) using typed first-order logic formulas. A *function contract* includes preconditions (**requires** clauses) and postconditions (**ensures** clauses). In addition, variables and memory locations the function is allowed to modify are listed in **assigns** clauses. Loops require additional annotations (**loop invariant** and **loop assigns** clauses). The reader can find more information on ACSL in [7, 11]. To show that the given C program respects the behavior specified by its annotations, the WP plug-in [8] generates *proof goals* (also called *proof obligations* or *verification conditions*). Such goals are mostly proven automatically, either by internal formula simplifier Qed [17] or external SMT solvers, but in some cases manual intervention is required to help the simplifier and the solvers by creating a *proof script*, a sequence of applications of predefined proof tactics.

Sometimes, it is also possible to circumvent the (time-consuming) development of such a proof script by adding assertions (using an **assert** clause), which must hold at a precise program point inside the function and can act as intermediate lemmas for the proof of complex goals. Such **assert** clauses can also be generated by other plugins. In particular, RTE [29] automatically emits **assert** clauses that are necessary to prove the absence of runtime errors (or *undefined behaviors*, as defined in the C standard [31]). Indeed, they must be avoided to ensure the soundness of the verification and exclude potential security vulnerabilities they can enable (notably *buffer overflows*). WP generates proof goals for all assertions.

As illustrated in [9], there is a risk to introduce logical inconsistencies into specifications that are assumed, e.g. in entry-point function preconditions, environment hypotheses or postconditions of stub functions. WP can generate additional assertions to *try to detect* potential inconsistencies leading to logical contradictions. While very useful, this feature cannot guarantee the absence of inconsistencies, thus such specifications still must be carefully reviewed.

Verification can often benefit from *ghost code* [10, 20, 25], that is, additional C code added in annotations and used for verification only. It can create ghost C structures, possibly referring to structures of the original C code. Frama-C ensures non-interference of the ghost world into the non-ghost world: the semantics of the C code is not modified by ghost code.

Our decision to use Frama-C is due to its capacity to successfully verify industrial C code and the fact that it is currently the only tool for C code verification recognized by ANSSI, the French Common Criteria certification body, as an acceptable formal verification technique for the highest levels of certification [21].

3 Parser Security and Related Requirements

Parsers are generally complex and dangerous software. Indeed, parsed messages can contain a lot of interdependencies between particular message elements. The attacker’s control—full or even partial—over the parsed message can allow him to lead the processing system to unintended states and achieve practical exploits. This control can depend on the used cryptographic protections, the distance between the vulnerable parser and external interfaces, and other factors.

The most frequent parsing bugs are related to memory safety. All parsing steps must therefore access only valid memory of all involved buffers, in particular if this access is dependent on input data.

Numerous real-world exploits have been reported in last decades due to memory safety issues. For example, a simple overflow can lead to a segmentation error and a system crash, which can be exploited by attackers for denial-of-service attacks [14]. A buffer overflow during a reading operation, which relies on an incorrect buffer length from a malformed input message, can copy sensitive data from the victim’s memory and return it to the attacker, like in the HeartBleed vulnerability [2]. A buffer overflow during a writing operation can allow attackers to rewrite system metadata and get control over the subsequent execution [1].

Even when a message is cryptographically protected, a wrong interplay between the parser and the cryptographic module can lead to a loss of protection, for example, with an acceptance of unauthenticated data. Mechanisms of such a wrong cooperation differ. For example, the parser can return different data than the previously authenticated by the module [27]. For the case of PKCS#1 v1.5 signature, RSA cryptographic strength is dependent on added padding that enforces modular exponentiation, a key operation used in RSA. The security of the whole signature scheme is thus dependent on the security of its message parser. Many bugs also come from arithmetical overflows [40], which can lead the program to unintended states and trigger some of the previous issues.

Let us state general requirements that will be refined and formalized below for the PKCS#1 v1.5 case (“sec” and “comp” stand for security and compatibility).

\mathcal{R}_{mem} : Parser processing must be memory-safe. All memory accesses must be done to valid memory.

$\mathcal{R}_{\text{arith}}$: Parser processing must be free of arithmetical overflows, except well-justified cases.

\mathcal{R}_{sec} : If the parser accepts a message (and extracts its data), it must enforce all checks necessary to ensure it has correct format and content.

$\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$: If the parser refuses an input message, it must be based on a check, clearly showing that the message’s format or content is incorrect. In that case, no already extracted data should be further processed.

4 PKCS#1 Signature Parser and Its Security

PKCS#1 (Public-Key Cryptography Standard) [41] specifies the usage of RSA algorithm [48], in particular for creation and verification of signatures. PKCS#1 signatures are used to protect X.509 certificates [16]. To enforce security, *padding schemes* (defining how additional padding should be used) are prescribed to be applied with an RSA operation. Although PKCS#1 v1.5 is an older signature padding scheme², it is still widely used for backward-compatibility. For example, the newest version of TLS [47] mandates its support for certificate signature verification. Next to that, it is still a valid option within SSH [51] and IPsec protocols [34, 42]. For those reasons, it still remains a target for attackers today.

4.1 TLV-based Message Structure

TLV-based structure. We denote the byte length of a data structure v by $\text{len}(v)$. The structure of messages manipulated by parsers is often based on *Tag-Length-Value triples*, or *TLVs*. A TLV $\theta = (t, l, v)$ contains three consecutive fields: a tag t used to identify the type of the TLV, a length field l containing the byte length of its value field, and a value field v containing the value. In other words, we have $l = \text{len}(v)$. The byte length of the whole TLV θ is the sum of the lengths of its fields, that is, $\text{len}(\theta) = \text{len}(t) + \text{len}(l) + \text{len}(v) = \text{len}(t) + \text{len}(l) + l$.

TLVs can be nested. Following [32], we say that a TLV is *constructed* if its value field contains a sequence of one or several TLVs. Otherwise, a TLV is called *primitive*. A TLV structure creates a tree, where constructed and primitive TLVs correspond, resp., to parent nodes and to leaves. Using this tree-based terminology we can speak of a TLV *level* (i.e., a depth in the tree) and define a parent-child relation between TLVs.

Fig. 1: PKCS#1 v1.5 signature: an ASN.1 structure with 5 nested TLVs preceded by a padding.

DigestInfo/SEQUENCE in the standard) is constructed. It contains in its value field V_1 two other TLVs at Level 2: a TLV $\theta_2 = (T_2, L_2, V_2)$ (of type DigestAlgorithm/SEQUENCE in the standard) and a TLV $\theta_3 = (T_3, L_3, V_3)$ with a string of bytes (of type OCTET STRING in the standard). It means that V_1 consecutively stores the fields of θ_2 and θ_3 . The latter is primitive. θ_2 is constructed again and contains two TLVs at Level 3, $\theta_4 = (T_4, L_4, V_4)$ (of type Object Identifier, or OID, in the standard) and $\theta_5 = (T_5, L_5, V_5)$ (of type NULL in the standard) containing a value V_5 of length $L_5 = 0$, i.e., an empty value with no bytes.

Example of TLVs. Consider the signature structure illustrated in Fig. 1, which is used by the target parser as detailed below. For the moment, we ignore the padding bytes on the left. At the upper level—Level 1—TLV $\theta_1 = (T_1, L_1, V_1)$ (of type

² for new applications, it is superseded by PKCS#1-PSS.

Correct message format and content. Following [13], we informally define two properties. A message has a *correct format* if it has the expected TLV structure (with tags specified in [41]), and its constructed TLVs verify property $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$:

$\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$: For a constructed TLV $\theta = (t, l, v)$ whose value contains a sequence of n TLVs θ_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), the length of the value field of θ is the sum of lengths of its children θ_i , that is, $l = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{len}(\theta_i)$.

A message has a *correct content* if all its primitive TLVs have expected content, i.e. expected values of its length and value fields.

4.2 Algorithm Description

Overview. PKCS#1 v2.2 specification defines PKCS#1 v1.5 signature scheme as a *signature with appendix*. As depicted in Fig. 2, during the signature creation procedure, the input message M is hashed, encoded, padded, and signed. The signature is the result of the RSA private key operation on a fully padded encoded message. This signature is then attached to the input message. Both are later required for signature verification, which can be done in several ways.

Signature creation. First, the hash operation (going from Step 0 to 1) provides a hash $H(M)$. It is then encoded into a so-called ASN.1 structure (Step 1 to 2). This is the nested TLVs structure shown in Fig. 1, which contains two main pieces of information: the OID identifier of the used hash function (θ_4) and the resulting hash value $H(M)$ of the input message (θ_3). An additional tag (θ_5) can host a hash parameter. For the SHA family of hashes, it should be NULL.

Next, a padding is added as a prefix to the ASN.1 structure (Step 2 to 3). It consists of two fixed bytes 0x00 and 0x01, followed by a variable-length sequence of padding bytes 0xFF, and finished by a delimiter byte 0x00, which separates it from the ASN.1 structure. The implementation of the resulting padded message is shown in Fig. 1. The number of padding bytes is chosen to achieve the message size required by the following RSA operation, that is, the size of RSA modulus.³

Correct signatures must satisfy two properties. First, the OID TLV must correspond to the ID of a hash function in the standard, and known to the parser. Second, the size of the hash value must correspond to this hash function.

Signature verification. Because of the deterministic nature of PKCS#1 v1.5 signature padding, it is possible to apply different approaches to signature verification, as depicted in Fig. 2. First, the Encoding approach—the main procedure presented in [41]—does not actually involve any parsing. Given an input message M and a hash function, M is re-encoded (Steps 0 to 3) and then compared byte-by-byte with the result of the RSA operation (using a public key to reverse from signature to padded message, Step 4 to 3). Omitting the parsing steps avoids a difficult situation, where all variants of Bleichenbacher’s attack were reported.

³ this size defines the strength of an RSA operation, e.g. 1024 bits or 2048 bits.

Fig. 2: PKCS#1 v1.5: creating a signature for message M (on the left) and three approaches for verification of the signature of message M (on the right).

However, the specification [41] also allows an alternative, the Decoding approach. There, the padded message content is parsed to extract the message hash (Steps 4 to 1). If the extracted hash is equal to the re-computed one (Step 0 to 1), the signature is accepted. To be secure, the parser must check for correctness of the message format and content. Compared to the

previous one, this approach avoids allocating space for the re-encoded message, which has the RSA modulus size.

As reported in [50], many libraries use a Hybrid approach. They parse only the padding (cf. Fig. 1) and then extract the entire ASN.1 structure (Steps 4 to 2). The latter is not parsed, but instead compared, as in the Encoding approach, against the re-encoded structure (Steps 0 to 2). This approach seems a reasonable trade-off. Parsing of ASN.1, which is structurally complex, is avoided, resulting in a higher security assurance. At the same time, the ASN.1 structure is relatively small compared to modulus size, thus reducing memory space overhead. In this work, we focus on the Decoding approach, which contains complex parsing steps and is therefore the most relevant for formal verification.

DER encoding and unique binary representation. One possible way to encode TLVs at binary level is defined by *DER (Distinguished Encoding Rules)* [32]. We also use it in our parser. The latest standard [41] mandates the use of DER for the creation of new signatures. DER ensures a *unique binary representation* of the data in the TLVs. When DER is used in PKCS#1 v1.5 to encode ASN.1, each of the tag and length fields of its TLVs is stored in *exactly one byte*.

Backward-compatibility. As it often happens in practice, evolution of software impacts compatibility. To ensure backward-compatibility, the standard [41] contains two requirements, which break the uniqueness of binary representation of the message: an *optional* presence of the NULL TLV⁴ and support of another encoding, *BER (Basic Encoding Rules)* [32]. For simplicity, we do not support these requirements in this work (see also Sect. 4.4).

4.3 Signature Security

As already mentioned in Sect. 3, RSA security depends on the padding scheme. If the parser does not strictly check correct format and content of the padded

⁴ This requirement is ignored by many open-source libraries [50] including OpenSSL v3.5, see <https://openssl-library.org/source>.

message (State 3 of Fig. 2), it may lead to *universal signature forgery*, meaning that the attacker is able to create another actor’s signature for *any* given message so that the resulting signature will be accepted by signature verification.

Since Bleichenbacher’s original attack [26] reported in 2006, many variants have been found for the Decoding and Hybrid approaches. The attack is possible under the following two conditions. First, the signature must be verified using a public key of a specific small size— typically with public key exponent equal to 3— which is already rarely seen in practice [50], yet it can be found in sensitive parts of the cryptographic ecosystem. For example, in 2021, Debian trust-anchor certificate bundle (ca-certificate) contained two certificates with such keys [50]. Four years later, they are still present on Ubuntu (22.04.4).

Second, the verification procedure must ignore a sufficient number of bytes inside a padded message. Using the ignored bytes, an attacker can manage to compute a fake signature such that a public key operation on it—that is, taking a power of 3 *without modulo computation* in this case due to a small value— matches the data inside the checked bytes, such as the input message’s hash. Note that it is impossible to avoid modulo computation if no byte inside a padded message is ignored and all are checked to some concrete values. Such a computation is then considered infeasible without knowledge of the private key.

Bleichenbacher’s attack variants differ in locations that the buggy parser ignores. The original report [26] found parsers that ignored trailing bytes at the end of the padded message, i.e., after a correct ASN.1 structure. In [36, 43], the length field in the NULL TLV was not checked and its value skipped. Another variant [30] ignored bytes in an extended form of the length field due to an arithmetic overflow. In another variant [13], padding bytes were not checked.

We can now formulate a security property, which refines \mathcal{R}_{sec} for the PKCS#1 v1.5 parser and gives a sufficient condition to rule out such attacks.

$\mathcal{P}_{\text{uniq}}$: The parser accepts a padded message (depicted at State 3 in Fig. 2) only if it checks its every byte for a unique correct value determined by input message M and hash function according to the PKCS#1 v1.5 specification.

4.4 Target Parser Implementation

We apply the verification on a PKCS#1 v1.5 signature parser that we implemented in C. It follows the Decoding approach, which is more bug-prone and thus more relevant for verification. Its three main functions perform the parsing. Function `pars_pkcs1_level1` is the parser’s entry point. It removes the padding and realizes checks for the TLV at Level 1 (cf. Fig. 1). It expects two buffers (see line 649 of Fig. 7): the padded message (`pad_msg` of size `pad_msg_sz`), which is the output of an RSA operation on signature (State 3 in Fig 2), and the input message M (`in_msg` of size `in_msg_sz`). Its callee, function `pars_pkcs1_level2`, handles the nested TLVs (Levels 2 and 3) and makes all semantic checks for the primitive TLVs’ content. Repetitive steps for parsing a TLV are encapsulated in function `read_one_tlv`. The value returned by the parser either indicates that all checks pass, or provides an error code.

```

6 typedef unsigned char ul;
7 typedef unsigned int uint;

70 /*@ ghost
71 const uint g_tlv_1[4] = {1, TAG_SEQ, CONSTR, 1};
72 const uint g_tlv_2[7] = {2, TAG_SEQ, CONSTR, 2, TAG_OCT, PRIM, 0};
73 const uint g_tlv_3[7] = {2, TAG_OID, PRIM, 0, TAG_NULL, PRIM, 0};
74
75 \ghost const uint* const g_tlv_spec[3] =
76   { &g_tlv_1[0], &g_tlv_2[0], &g_tlv_3[0] };
77
78 ul* g_tlv_1_p[1]; ul* g_tlv_2_p[2]; ul* g_tlv_3_p[2];
79
80 ul* \ghost * const g_tlv_p[3] =
81   { &g_tlv_1_p[0], &g_tlv_2_p[0], &g_tlv_3_p[0] }; */

```

Fig. 3: Basic types and a ghost model of the TLV structure of ASN.1.

Our verification perimeter does not include the RSA operation, but includes a call to a hash computation (modeled by one of the three stub functions `stub_shaX`). This allows us to extend our properties to check that a proper hash function was indeed applied. As it is common for open-source libraries, the chosen hash function is indicated by an input parameter (`expect_hash_ind`, see lines 649–650 of Fig. 7), expected to be a valid index in the list of supported hashes (see line 597). It allows the parser to check the hash function used inside the signature (as stored in the OID TLV) to any declaration external to PKCS#1 (e.g., the hash function declaration in the field of a X.509 certificate).

As it is essential for secure parsing programming, we chose a clear parsing pattern for our code, i.e., it parses all TLVs of the same sequence and checks $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$ property with respect to its parent before starting to parse its children. Similarly, before starting to read a new TLV (in function `read_one_tlv`), we check that reading indexes are inside valid memory.

Our parser supports three hash functions (SHA256, SHA512, and, for backward compatibility, SHA1). Adding new functions is straightforward. The complete code is provided in the companion artifact. For lack of space, only essential (slightly simplified) parts are presented in Figs. 3–7, in which we preserve the line numbers of the complete file for convenience of the readers.

5 Formal ACSL Properties and Verification Approach

Correct message format (incl. $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$). To describe TLV-based structures, our methodology strongly relies on *inductive predicate* definitions in ACSL. Indeed, due to the structural nature of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$, it is convenient to inductively define the correctness of a parsing step, as well as to maintain information about the already (correctly) parsed elements of the structure in the form of an inductive predicate. An interesting feature of the approach is that those predicates are *generic*, and are parameterized by a concrete TLV structure, defined as a *ghost model*.

Figure 3 presents the ghost model of the ASN.1 structure (cf. Fig. 1). The ghost models of the sequences of TLVs at Levels 1–3 are encoded, resp., in arrays `g_tlv_N` with $N \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ (see lines 71–73 in Fig. 3). The first byte indicates the number of TLVs in the sequence. The next bytes store the descriptions for each TLV of the sequence. Each description is composed of three bytes. The first

```

86 inductive valid_tlv(ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
87   integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, boolean with_children)
88 {
89 case empty: \forall ul* start, integer tlv_id;
90   valid_tlv(start, 0, 0, 0, tlv_id, \true);
91
92 case new_tlv_child_not_incl:
93   \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
94     integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id;
95   \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
96   0 <= tlv_num_pars < tlv_cur[0] &&
97   valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true) &&
98   start[size_pars] == (ul)tlv_cur[1 + tlv_num_pars*3]
99   ==>
100  valid_tlv(start, size_pars, size_pars + 2 + start[size_pars + 1],
101    tlv_num_pars+1, tlv_id, \false);
102  ...
103 case last_tlv_constr_incl_child:
104   \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
105     integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, integer nest_prev_pars;
106   \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
107   \let tlv_link = tlv_cur[3 + (tlv_num_pars-1)*3];
108   1 <= tlv_num_pars &&
109   valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
110   (ul)tlv_cur[2 + (tlv_num_pars-1)*3] == CONSTR &&
111   valid_tlv(start + prev_pars + 2, nest_prev_pars, start[prev_pars + 1],
112     g_tlv_spec[tlv_link][0], tlv_link, \true)
113   ==>
114   valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true); }

```

Fig. 4: Inductive predicate for correct message format.

and the second bytes indicate, resp., the expected tag and TLV type (constructed or primitive). For a primitive TLV, the third byte contains a dummy value (here, 0, cf. lines 72, 73). For a constructed TLV, the third byte is used to find the ghost model of the child sequence of TLVs. It is indicated indirectly, as an index in the ghost array `g_tlv_spec` (cf. lines 75–76) that stores pointers to the ghost models of TLV sequences. For instance, index 2 on line 72 refers to the sequence of Level 3 since the element of index 2 in `g_tlv_spec` is `&g_tlv_3[0]`. The `\ghost` keyword indicates that the pointed arrays are also ghost. As shown in Fig. 1, each TLV level contains one sequence of TLVs in our case⁵. Lines 78–81 of Fig. 3 will be explained below.

The `valid_tlv` inductive predicate (see Fig. 4) states that a given TLV sequence has a correct format (so far). It takes 6 arguments. First, parameter `start` points to a location where the parsing of the TLV sequence begins. The number of already consumed bytes and already parsed TLVs are given, resp., in `size_pars` and `tlv_num_pars`. The ghost model of the target TLV sequence is indicated as its index within `g_tlv_spec` by `tlv_id`. The last two parameters are more technical, related to the current stage of the parsing. Parameter `with_child` indicates whether child TLV sequences were already resolved (that is, checked) for the last parsed TLV, as described below. Lastly, `prev_pars` is the number of bytes consumed before parsing the last parsed TLV.

⁵ In general, there will be n sequences of TLVs at Level $k + 1$ if at Level k we have n TLVs having a child sequence.

For example, consider the TLV structure of Fig. 1 and assume θ_1 starts at p . When the parsing of TLV θ_1 is correctly finished at Level 1, before checking the child sequence, we have (i) `valid_tlv(p, 0, 2+L1, 1, 0, \false)`, and (ii) `valid_tlv(p, 0, 2+L1, 1, 0, \true)` after checking the child sequence. The latter step requires a correct format of the sequence at Level 2, leading after parsing θ_2 (and its child sequence) to (iii) `valid_tlv(p+2, 0, 2+L2, 1, 1, \true)` and finally to (iv) `valid_tlv(p+2, 2+L2, 4+L2+L3, 2, 1, \true)` after parsing θ_3 . Recall that the ghost models of Levels 1,2 are, resp., at indices 0,1 in `g_tlv_spec`. To respect $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$, L_1 must be equal to $4 + L_2 + L_3$.

Each induction step is defined by one case. Case `empty` initializes the induction for a starting pointer and a ghost model, with no parsed bytes and no parsed TLVs (lines 89–90 in Fig. 4). Next, case `new_tlv_child_not_incl` (lines 92–101) parses another TLV in the sequence. The tag and the number of TLVs are checked according to the ghost model (lines 95–96, 98), the size of the new TLV is added to the number of parsed bytes and the number of parsed TLVs is incremented (lines 100–101). After this step, `with_child` is `false`. This indicates that for the last parsed TLV, the child sequence has yet to be checked against the specification.

To deduce a full validity (i.e., with `with_child` set to `true`) for the last parsed TLV, we introduce two other cases, resp., for a constructed and a primitive TLV. Case `last_tlv_constr_incl_child` is applied if the last parsed TLV θ is constructed and its child sequence has not yet been checked (lines 119–120). This step requires that the child TLV sequence be correctly processed, including their own children if any (lines 121–122): an expected number of TLVs with expected tags must be parsed. The ghost model of the child sequence is identified according to that of the parent (line 117). Property $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$ is ensured for θ and its children. The case for a primitive TLV is trivial (switching `with_child` to `true`), and is omitted here.

In the previous example, step `last_tlv_constr_incl_child` is used to deduce (ii) from (i) and (iv). The reader can check by a step-by-step application that it works only if $L_1 = 4 + L_2 + L_3$, thus ensuring $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$.

Correct message content. According to [41] (and using the notation of Fig. 1), a valid message content must satisfy the following properties for primitive TLVs.

- \mathcal{P}_1 : The parsed OID (fields L_4 and V_4) corresponds to the indicated hash function (in the entry point function parameter `expect_hash_ind`).
- \mathcal{P}_2 : The length of NULL TLV (field L_5) is equal to 0.
- \mathcal{P}_3 : The length of the parsed hash value (L_3) corresponds to the parsed OID.
- \mathcal{P}_4 : The function used for hash re-computation corresponds to the parsed OID.
- \mathcal{P}_5 : Hash re-computation is applied on input message M (in the entry point function parameter `in_msg`).
- \mathcal{P}_6 : The parsed hash value (V_3) is equal to the re-computed hash value.

Since our inductive predicate `valid_tlv` focuses on the correct format in a generic way and does not trace particular TLVs, we cannot use it to identify, e.g., θ_4 for validating \mathcal{P}_1 when looking at the message as a whole. Similarly, as

```

193 predicate prim_tlv_oid_param(integer exp_hash_ind) =
194   \let oid_len = *(g_tlv_p[2][0]+1);           // Reads L4
195   \let oid_val_p = g_tlv_p[2][0]+2;           // Points to V4
196   \let param_len = *(g_tlv_p[2][1]+1);       // Reads L5
197   (oid_len == OID_list[exp_hash_ind][0]) &&   // En-
198   same_content(OID_list[exp_hash_ind]+1, oid_val_p, oid_len) && // sures P1
199   param_len == 0;                             // Ensures P2

```

Fig. 5: \mathcal{P}_1 and \mathcal{P}_2 : content properties related to OID and NULL TLVs.

```

227 /*@ ghost
228 ul g_backup_mes_to_hash[INT_MAX];
229 uint g_backup_len;
230
231 /*@ requires \valid_read(msg + (0 .. msg_sz-1));
232   terminates \true; exits \false;
233   assigns g_backup_mes_to_hash[0 .. msg_sz-1];
234   ensures same_content(msg, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
235   ensures g_backup_len == msg_sz; @/
236 void g_make_backup(ul* msg, int msg_sz); */

```

Fig. 6: Ghost array and function for creating a memory snapshot.

we can see for example for \mathcal{P}_3 , there are dependencies between different TLVs, sometimes from different TLV levels. We detail here only \mathcal{P}_1 , \mathcal{P}_2 and \mathcal{P}_5 .

To express these properties, we introduce a ghost array `g_tlv_p` (see lines 78–81 of Fig. 3), whose structure and size are similar to `g_tlv_spec`. During the parsing, we store—via ghost code—pointers to the beginning of each primitive TLV at the corresponding locations of this array. Once the parsing is completed, it allows us to refer to any primitive TLV. For instance, `g_tlv_p[2][0]` stores a pointer to the first TLV (second index 0) in the TLV sequence at Level 3 (first index 2), that is, to θ_4 . Added ghost code is simple—it stores a pointer to each primitive TLV into the corresponding array element. It is however mandatory to add it for all primitive TLVs. To avoid any mistake, we introduce a second inductive predicate `prim_gh_set`. Structurally, it mimics `valid_tlv` presented above, with two important differences: it does not check again the expected tag, and it requires `g_tlv_p` to be correctly assigned with pointers to primitive TLVs. By maintaining `prim_gh_set` together with `valid_tlv`, we ensure that the message was checked for correct format and all pointers to primitive TLVs were correctly set, being readily available for content verifications.

Figure 5 shows a predicate to check \mathcal{P}_1 and \mathcal{P}_2 . On lines 194–196, the OID and NULL TLVs (θ_4 and θ_5) are accessed. To get the OID length L_4 we first find θ_4 , the first TLV at level 3, by a pointer `g_tlv_p[2][0]`. This gives us the address of T_4 . We increment it by 1 to get the address of L_4 , that we dereference to get its value. Line 197–198 check V_4 (including its length L_4) to have the expected value from list of supported hash functions `OID_list`. On line 199 we then check L_5 to be 0.

Ghost code is also used to store necessary information for the proof of \mathcal{P}_4 and \mathcal{P}_5 . Let us detail \mathcal{P}_5 here. It requires to check that the hash function is applied indeed on the *original* message. To keep a copy of the message, we introduce a ghost array `g_backup_mes_to_hash` and a stub function `g_make_backup` (see Fig. 6). Its contract ensures that the function copies the content of the input

into the ghost array. We call it at the very beginning of the entry point function (line 652 of Fig. 7). To verify \mathcal{P}_5 at a hash computation, typically realized by a crypto library call, it is sufficient to add a precondition checking that the content of its input array is identical to the one saved in `g_backup_mes_to_hash`. The strong separation of the non-ghost world from the ghost one enforced by Frama-C [4] excludes unintended modifications of `g_backup_mes_to_hash` in the C code, thus making this approach consistent.

Entry point function contract. Figure 7 shows the contract for the entry point function, `pars_PKCS1_level`. Several predicates are introduced to deal with the padding shown in Fig. 1. Predicate `prefix_prop` expresses the presence of the two fixed prefix bytes (lines 557–558). Then, `padding_prop` requires a variable length sequence containing (at least `MIN_FF_COUNT`) times `0xFF` and finished by a delimiter byte (at offset `pad_bound`). Predicate `asn_prop` states that the Level 1 ASN.1 TLV is correctly formatted (using `valid_tlv`) and occupies the entire space between the delimiter and the end of the padded message. As we already explained, it is valid only if all its TLV descendants were correctly parsed too. Predicate `ghost_set_prop` ensures that referenced ghost pointers were set correctly. Regarding message content properties, \mathcal{P}_1 – \mathcal{P}_4 and \mathcal{P}_6 are regrouped in predicate `prim_tlv` (not detailed here, used on line 625), while \mathcal{P}_5 is ensured at another location.

\mathcal{R}_{sec} and $\mathcal{P}_{\text{uniq}}$. As we can see on lines 614–625 of Fig.7, if the parser accepts the message, the conjunction of all predicates above must hold. We recall there are 3 primitive TLVs within ASN.1 structure: θ_3 , θ_4 and θ_5 . One can easily see that properties \mathcal{P}_1 – \mathcal{P}_6 specify all bytes of fields L_i , V_i for $3 \leq i \leq 5$ ⁶ by making them uniquely determined by the input message and expected hash function. Indeed, for example on lines 197–198 of Fig. 5, we specify all bytes of L_4 and V_4 when we match parsed OID against parser list of supported OIDs. Inductive predicate `valid_tlv` then provides unique specification for all TLV tags. Next to that, due to $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$, lengths of constructed TLVs are uniquely determined by the contained primitive TLVs. Based on this analysis of our properties, we see that the proved parser indeed *accepts only one padded message* for each input message and expected hash function and so it fulfills $\mathcal{P}_{\text{uniq}}$. As explained in Sect.4.3, this guarantees its security against Bleichenbacher’s attack family.

$\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$. We formalize our properties for $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ on lines 627–647 of Fig.7. The specification is split based on the error type: for example, if an error is returned for insufficient space during the parsing of a new TLV, an unexpected tag or an inconsistent TLV structure (with regard to $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$), it implies a falsification of `valid_tlv` (lines 635–638). In case an error indicates a wrong content, we prove a correct setting of ghost pointers and a falsification of content properties (lines 640–647). An additional reason to split `prim_gh_set` and `valid_tlv` into two separate predicates—despite their similar structure—is the following.

⁶ V_5 is absent as L_5 is equal to 0.

```

556 /*@ ghost uint pad_bound;*/
557 /*@ predicate prefix_prop(ul* pad_msg) =
558   pad_msg[OFF_B1] == EXP_B1 && pad_msg[OFF_B2] == EXP_B2;
559 predicate padding_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound)=
560   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
561   (\forall integer padd_off; 2 <= padd_off < pad_bound ==>
562     pad_msg[padd_off] == EXP_FF) && pad_msg[pad_bound] == EXP_DELIM;
563 predicate asn_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound,
564   integer tlv_num) =
565   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
566   \exists integer prev_pars; valid_tlv(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1, prev_pars,
567     pad_msg_sz - pad_bound - 1, tlv_num, 0, \true);
568 predicate ghost_set_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound,
569   integer tlv_num)=
570   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
571   \exists integer prev_pars; prim_gh_set(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1, prev_pars,
572     pad_msg_sz - pad_bound - 1, tlv_num, 0, \true); */
...
595 requires \valid(pad_msg + (0 .. pad_msg_sz-1));
596 requires \valid(in_msg + (0 .. in_msg_sz - 1));
597 requires 0 <= expect_hash_ind < SUPP_OID_COUNT;
...
614 // ===== SECURITY PART =====
615 behavior sec_format:
616   ensures prefix: \result == PASS_OK ==> prefix_prop(pad_msg);
617   ensures pad: \result == PASS_OK ==>
618     padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound);
619   ensures asn: \result == PASS_OK ==>
620     asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
621
622 behavior sec_prim_tlv:
623   ensures ghost_set: \result == PASS_OK ==>
624     ghost_set_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
625   ensures prim_tlv: \result == PASS_OK ==> prim_tlv(expect_hash_ind);
626
627 // ===== COMPATIBILITY (ACCEPTANCE) PART =====
628 behavior acc_format:
629   ensures prefix:
630     \result == ERR_B1 || \result == ERR_B2 ==> !prefix_prop(pad_msg);
631   ensures pad:
632     \result == ERR_FF_COUNT || \result == ERR_DELIM ==>
633     \forall uint pad_bound; !padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound) ||
634     !asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
635   ensures asn:
636     \result == ERR_LEN || \result == ERR_TAG || \result == ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST ==>
637     \forall uint pad_bound; !padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound) ||
638     !asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
639
640 behavior acc_prim_tlv:
641   ensures ghost_set:
642     \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_HASH_VAL ||
643     \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==>
644     ghost_set_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
645   ensures prim_tlv:
646     \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_HASH_VAL ||
647     \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==> prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
648 */
649 int pars_PKCS1_lvl1(ul* pad_msg, int pad_msg_sz, ul* in_msg, int in_msg_sz,
650   uint expect_hash_ind)
651 {
652   /*@ ghost g_make_backup(in_msg, in_msg_sz);

```

Fig. 7: Entry point parser contract.

Predicate `prim_gh_set` can be falsified also by a buggy ghost code, (i.e. a mistake made during proof development). On the other hand, $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ requires

that the parser returns an error code only based on a wrong message format or content. Inside our specification, we therefore cannot allow the parser to refuse the message based on a failure of `prim_gh_set`.

\mathcal{R}_{mem} and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{arith}}$. \mathcal{R}_{mem} and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{arith}}$ are checked by annotations automatically generated by RTE (see Sect. 3). We specify a precondition of the entry point function, claiming memory validity of both input buffers (lines 595–596 of Fig. 7). Regarding $\mathcal{R}_{\text{arith}}$, as explained in [29], some arithmetic overflows (e.g. for char or unsigned integers) fall into the category of implementation-defined or even well-defined behavior and thus are not checked by RTE by default. In our verification, we also activate the corresponding checks to avoid any overflows.

Current limitations and perspectives of extension. While this case study already targets a representative parser, our approach may require extensions for the verification of other PKCS#1 v1.5 parser implementations or different TLV-based protocol. We currently consider the Decoding approach, with 1-byte fields both for a tag and a length field, and a mandatory presence of a NULL TLV. Extensions to support other choices are left as future work.

6 Proof Results

Summary of results. We use Framac v. 29.0 (Copper) with external SMT prover Alt-Ergo 2.5.4. on a VM running Ubuntu 24.04 under VirtualBox (running on a host PC under Windows 10 with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 CPU @ 2.70GHz) with 4 processors and 8 GB dedicated to the VM. The verified parser (155 lines of C code) includes seven C functions (including three stubs) annotated with 364 lines⁷ of ACSL, giving a 2.35 spec-to-code ratio. To show the absence of runtime errors, we use the RTE plugin, which automatically generates 52 asserts.

Overall, the WP plugin generates and successfully proves 434 proof goals. Among them, reachability analysis proves 4 goals. The internal WP simplifier, Qed, discharges 251 goals. Alt-Ergo solves 176 goals. 3 goals require manually created WP proof scripts. The whole proof (with additional 60 consistency checks activated by `-wp-smoke-tests`) takes 2 min 8 s, with up to 14.2 s for one proof goal. We estimate the total effort to perform the verification case study (incl. creating a suitable methodology for a new kind of target code, identifying properties, annotating code and creating necessary proof scripts) as 6 person-months. Acquiring necessary expertise in cybersecurity and proof is not included in it.

Selected difficulties. The created proof scripts instantiate the most complex induction step of `valid_tlv` (see line 113 in Fig. 4) and `prim_gh_set`, which check the nested TLV structure. Next to that, we use several **assert** clauses, which further help us to instantiate other steps of these inductive predicates. It is for example necessary for each TLV sequence to initialize induction.

⁷ We apply `cloc` utility. It considers ACSL annotations as other C comments. We thus removed classical C comments to count ACSL. Empty lines in C code are ignored.

In our work, we experienced a specific difficulty with proofs involving inductive predicates. Indeed, in some cases, an assignment to an unrelated memory location would cause previously established instances of the inductive predicate to be “forgotten” by the prover. We worked around this issue by adding **assert** clauses for initial induction steps after the writing. This is not a universal solution and another methodology might be needed in other cases.

7 Related Work and Conclusion

Related work. Various approaches using formal methods were already applied on parsers. Symbolic execution and adaptive combinatorial testing were used to generate test suites and to discover a significant number of bugs in PKCS#1 v1.5 signature verification of public cryptographic libraries [13, 50]. Formal verification was deployed [19, 50] using Coq and Agda, providing test oracles and a reference implementation of PKCS#1 v1.5 signature and X.509 certificate validation logic. However, proof was not performed for efficient real-life parsers. Ramananandro et al. developed an automatic parser generator, formally proven in F*, and extracted C code using a non-verified tool [46]. Although it can serve to generate a big amount of parser code automatically [49], some validation logic is not expressible and the corresponding code must be added manually [19]. Li et al. used ACL2 formal language and developed a formally verified PDF parser and a semantic validator [39]. However, the correspondence between a formally verified ACL2 code and an efficient C code was not proved.

More generally, this work is related to other verification case studies [28]. Various verification tools were applied to verify real-life code, including KeY [6, 18], VerCors [3, 44], Frama-C [20, 22, 24], SPARK [15, 23], VCC [37], Dafny [12, 38], VeriFast [33, 45] and many others. Each new case study contributes to enhance verification tools by identifying their limitations and to push further the frontiers of what is achievable for formal verification.

Conclusion and future work. We have proposed a *methodology for formal verification* of a PKCS#1 v1.5 parser in Frama-C, and successfully *verified a representative parser* written in C. The proven properties include *security*, protecting against any variant of *Bleichenbacher’s attack* and ensuring *memory safety*, and *compatibility*, i.e. non-rejection of a correct signature. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that formal verification is applied directly on the C implementation of such a parser. Future work includes extensions to support additional features (see the end of Sect. 5), and formal verification of real-life open-source C parsers. We believe that our methodology also provides a basis for future extensions to other TLV-based formats, like X.509 certificates [16].

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A Appendix: Supplementary Material

This appendix is added for convenience of the reviewers, not for publication.

This appendix partly describes the companion artifact that the authors plan to make publicly available and to submit for artifact evaluation if the paper is accepted. It includes the annotated parser code, proof scripts and a few buggy versions of the parser, which illustrate the effectiveness of the proof to detect security and compatibility issues.

The proof was run with **Frama-C** v. 29.0 (Copper) with external SMT prover **Alt-Ergo** 2.5.4, on a VM running Ubuntu 24.04 under VirtualBox of version 7.0.14. The host PC runs Windows 10 (with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 CPU @ 2.70GHz) with 4 processors and 8 GB dedicated to the VM. The VM was tested with VirtualBox version 7.0.14.

A.1 The Complete PKCS#1 v1.5 Parser Code

Listing 1.1 gives the complete code of the target PKCS#1 v1.5 parser including ACSL annotations. The scope and signatures of the included functions are discussed in Sect. 4.4. The parser was successfully proven using **Frama-C** 29.0 (Copper) and SMT solver **Alt-Ergo** 2.5.4. The full command launching the proof is given in the beginning of the file. Three **Frama-C ensures** are not proven automatically and require additional proof scripts. They are used for instantiation of the two inductive steps, which handle constructed TLV child, namely `gh_last_tlv_constr_incl_child` and `last_tlv_constr_incl_child`). To trigger this instantiation inside the interactive **Frama-C**/WP GUI, we put additional asserts at the end of function `pars_PKCS1_level`. The related proof scripts are part of the artifact.

Listing 1.1: Complete annotated code of the PKCS#1 v1.5 parser.

```

1 // proven with:
2 // frama-c -wp -wp-rte -wp-timeout 30 -wp-session folder_with_scripts
3 // -wp-smoke-tests -wp-check-memory-model -warn-unsigned-overflow
4 // -warn-signed-downcast -warn-unsigned-downcast -wp-prover=script,Alt-Ergo
5 #include "limits.h"
6 typedef unsigned char ul;
7 typedef unsigned int uint;
8
9 // Parsing errors // Unexpected:
10 #define ERR_B1 0x01 //First prefix byte
11 #define ERR_B2 0x02 //Second prefix byte
12 #define ERR_FF_COUNT 0x03 //Less than minimum of pad bytes
13 #define ERR_DELIM 0x04 //Delimiter between pad and ASN
14 #define ERR_TAG 0x05 //TLV Tag
15 #define ERR_LEN 0x06 //TLV Length
16 #define ERR_HASH_SZ 0x08 //Hash length
17 #define ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST 0x09 //Nesting TLV property
18 #define ERR_HASH_OID 0x0A //Hash identifier
19 #define ERR_NULL_SZ 0x0B //Hash paramater size
20 #define ERR_HASH_VAL 0x0C //Hash value
21 //Hash crypto call error
22 #define ERR_INTER_BAD_CRYPT 0xF2
23 // Nominal parsing case
24 #define PASS_OK 0
25 // Parsing offsets and lengths
26 #define OFF_B1 0 // Prefix padding byte 1 offset
27 #define OFF_B2 1 // Prefix padding byte 2 offset
28 #define LEN_TAGLEN 2 // Total length of 2 fields: TAG + LEN
29 // Expected values during parsing
30 #define EXP_B1 0x00 // Prefix padding byte 1
31 #define EXP_B2 0x01 // Prefix padding byte 2
32 #define EXP_FF 0xFF // Padding 0xFF sequence
33 #define EXP_DELIM 0x00 // Padding delimiter
34 #define MIN_FF_COUNT 0x08 // Minimal size of FF sequence
35 #define TAG_SEQ 0x30 // ASN.1 SEQUENCE Tag
36 #define TAG_OCT 0x04 // ASN.1 OCTET_STRING Tag
37 #define TAG_OID 0x06 // ASN.1 OID Tag
38 #define TAG_NULL 0x05 // ASN.1 NULL Tag
39 #define ASN_LEN_NULL 0x00 // ASN.1 NULL Length
40 // Supported hash functions
41 #define SUPP_OID_COUNT 3
42 #define MAX_HASH_SIZE 64
43 #define SHA256_SIZE 32
44 #define SHA512_SIZE 64
45 #define SHA1_SIZE 20
46
47 enum hash_functions {SHA256_INDEX, SHA512_INDEX, SHA1_INDEX};
48
49 // Element 0 contains size of OID, followed by its value
50 const ul SHA256_OID[10] = {0x09, 0x60, 0x86, 0x48, 0x01, 0x65, 0x03, 0x04, 0x02, 0x01};
51 const ul SHA512_OID[10] = {0x09, 0x60, 0x86, 0x48, 0x01, 0x65, 0x03, 0x04, 0x02, 0x03};
52 const ul SHA1_OID[7] = {0x05, 0x2B, 0x0E, 0x03, 0x02, 0x1A};
53
54 const ul* const OID_list[SUPP_OID_COUNT] =
55   {(ul*)&SHA256_OID[0], (ul*)&SHA512_OID[0], (ul*)&SHA1_OID[0]};
56
57 ul hash_res[MAX_HASH_SIZE]; // Working buffer for hash computation
58
59 const int hash_len_for_oid[SUPP_OID_COUNT]={SHA256_SIZE, SHA512_SIZE, SHA1_SIZE};
60
61 #define OFF_COUNT 0
62 #define SPEC_ITEM_SZ 3
63 #define OFF_TAG 1
64 #define OFF_TYPE 2
65 #define OFF_LINK 3
66 #define PRIM 1

```

```

67 #define CONSTR          0
68
69 // ===== TLV structure specification =====
70 /*@ ghost
71 const uint g_tlv_1[4] = {1, TAG_SEQ, CONSTR, 1};
72 const uint g_tlv_2[7] = {2, TAG_SEQ, CONSTR, 2, TAG_OCT, PRIM, 0};
73 const uint g_tlv_3[7] = {2, TAG_OID, PRIM, 0, TAG_NULL, PRIM, 0};
74
75 \ghost const uint* const g_tlv_spec[3] =
76   { &g_tlv_1[0], &g_tlv_2[0], &g_tlv_3[0] };
77
78 ul* g_tlv_1_p[1]; ul* g_tlv_2_p[2]; ul* g_tlv_3_p[2];
79
80 ul* \ghost * const g_tlv_p[3] =
81   { &g_tlv_1_p[0], &g_tlv_2_p[0], &g_tlv_3_p[0] }; */
82
83 // Correct structure of message with respect to TLV specification g_tlv_spec
84 /*@
85 // ===== Inductive predicate for correct message format =====
86 inductive valid_tlv(ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
87   integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, boolean with_children)
88 {
89   case empty: \forall ul* start, integer tlv_id;
90     valid_tlv(start, 0, 0, 0, tlv_id, \true);
91
92   case new_tlv_child_not_incl:
93     \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
94       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id;
95     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
96     0 <= tlv_num_pars < tlv_cur[OFF_COUNT] &&
97     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true) &&
98     start[size_pars] == (ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TAG + tlv_num_pars*SPEC_ITEM_SZ]
99     ==>
100     valid_tlv(start, size_pars, size_pars + 2 + start[size_pars + 1],
101       tlv_num_pars+1, tlv_id, \false);
102
103   case last_tlv_prim_incl_child:
104     \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
105       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id;
106     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
107     1 <= tlv_num_pars &&
108     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
109     (ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == PRIM
110     ==>
111     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true);
112
113   case last_tlv_constr_incl_child:
114     \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
115       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, integer nest_prev_pars;
116     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
117     \let tlv_link = tlv_cur[OFF_LINK + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ];
118     1 <= tlv_num_pars &&
119     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
120     (ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == CONSTR &&
121     valid_tlv(start + prev_pars + 2, nest_prev_pars, start[prev_pars + 1],
122       g_tlv_spec[tlv_link][OFF_COUNT], tlv_link, \true)
123     ==>
124     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true); }
125
126 // Supplementary predicate
127 // To ease instantiation of prim_gh_set manually asserted in the code
128 predicate prim_tlv_stored(ul* start, integer tlv_id, integer tlv_seq_id,
129   integer prev_pars) =
130   \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_seq_id];
131   \let tlv_p_curr = g_tlv_p[tlv_seq_id];
132   (ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_id-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == PRIM &&
133   tlv_p_curr[tlv_id-1] == &start[prev_pars];
134

```

```

135 // Ghost code correctly store pointers to all primitive TLVs
136 inductive prim_gh_set (ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
137   integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, boolean with_children)
138 {
139   case gh_empty: \forallall ul* start, integer tlv_id;
140     prim_gh_set (start, 0, 0, 0, tlv_id, \true);
141
142   case gh_new_tlv_child_not_incl:
143     \forallall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
144       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id;
145     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
146     0 <= tlv_num_pars < tlv_cur[OFF_COUNT] &&
147     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true)
148     ==>
149     prim_gh_set(start, size_pars, size_pars + 2 + start[size_pars + 1],
150       tlv_num_pars+1, tlv_id, \false);
151
152   case gh_last_tlv_prim_incl_child:
153     \forallall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
154       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id;
155     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
156     1 <= tlv_num_pars &&
157     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
158     prim_tlv_stored(start, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, prev_pars)
159     ==>
160     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true);
161
162   case gh_last_tlv_constr_incl_child:
163     \forallall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
164       integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, integer nest_prev_pars;
165     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
166     \let tlv_link = tlv_cur[OFF_LINK + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ];
167     1 <= tlv_num_pars &&
168     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
169     (ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == CONSTR &&
170     prim_gh_set(start + prev_pars + 2, nest_prev_pars, start[prev_pars + 1],
171       g_tlv_spec[tlv_link][OFF_COUNT], tlv_link, \true)
172     ==>
173     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true);
174 }*/
175
176 /*@ predicate same_content(ul* f, ul* s, int len) =
177   \forallall integer i; 0<= i < len ==> (f[i] == s[i]);
178 */
179
180 // Stores index of used hash function
181 /*@ ghost int g_hash_app; */
182
183 /* Primitive TLVs content
184   Refers pointers to TLVs stored inside g_tlv_p structure
185 P1. Parsed OID corresponds to inputted hash function
186 P2. Length of NULL TLV is equal to 0
187 P3. Parsed hash value length corresponds to parsed OID
188 P4. Function used for hash re-computation corresponds to parsed OID
189 P5. Hash re-computation is applied on input message M
190 P6. Parsed hash value is equal to re-computed hash value*/
191 /*@
192 // Properties P1 and P2
193 predicate prim_tlv_oid_param(integer exp_hash_ind) =
194   \let oid_len = *(g_tlv_p[2][0]+1); // Reads L4
195   \let oid_val_p = g_tlv_p[2][0]+2; // Points to V4
196   \let param_len = *(g_tlv_p[2][1]+1); // Reads L5
197   (oid_len == OID_list[exp_hash_ind][0]) && // En-
198   same_content(OID_list[exp_hash_ind]+1, oid_val_p, oid_len) && // sures P1
199   param_len == 0; // Ensures P2
200
201 // Properties P3 + P6,
202 // P4 (together with ghost code related to

```

```

203 // g_hash_app)
204 predicate prim_tlv_hash(integer exp_hash_ind) =
205   \let hash_len = *(g_tlv_p[1][1]+1); \let hash_value_p = g_tlv_p[1][1]+2;
206   hash_len == hash_len_for_oid[exp_hash_ind] &&
207   g_hash_app == exp_hash_ind &&
208   same_content(hash_value_p, &hash_res[0], hash_len);
209
210 // prim_tlv_hash_neg is not logical negation of prim_tlv_hash
211 predicate prim_tlv_hash_neg(integer exp_hash_ind) =
212   \let hash_len = *(g_tlv_p[1][1]+1); \let hash_value_p = g_tlv_p[1][1]+2;
213   !(hash_len == hash_len_for_oid[exp_hash_ind]) ||
214   (g_hash_app == exp_hash_ind &&
215   !same_content(hash_value_p, &hash_res[0], hash_len));
216
217 predicate prim_tlv(uint exp_hash_ind) =
218   0<= exp_hash_ind < SUPP_OID_COUNT &&
219   prim_tlv_oid_param(exp_hash_ind) && prim_tlv_hash(exp_hash_ind);
220
221 predicate prim_tlv_neg(uint exp_hash_ind) =
222   0<= exp_hash_ind < SUPP_OID_COUNT ==>
223   !prim_tlv_oid_param(exp_hash_ind) || prim_tlv_hash_neg(exp_hash_ind);
224 */
225
226 // Stores input data snapshot for later comparison
227 /*@ ghost
228 ul g_backup_mes_to_hash[INT_MAX];
229 uint g_backup_len;
230
231 /*@ requires \valid_read(msg + (0 .. msg_sz-1));
232   terminates \true; exits \false;
233   assigns g_backup_mes_to_hash[0 .. msg_sz-1];
234   ensures same_content(msg, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
235   ensures g_backup_len == msg_sz; @/
236 void g_make_backup(ul* msg, int msg_sz); */
237
238 /*
239 Params: arr1: input array 1 start
240         arr2: input array 2 start
241         len : length to compare
242 Returns: 0 if arr1 and arr2 has the same prefix of len bytes
243         1 otherwise */
244 /*@
245   requires \valid_read(arr1 + (0 .. len-1));
246   requires \valid_read(arr2 + (0 .. len-1));
247   requires len >=0;
248   assigns \nothing;
249   ensures (\result == (int)0) <==> same_content(arr1, arr2, len);
250 */
251 int cmp_arr(const ul* arr1, const ul* arr2, int len)
252 { /*@ loop assigns i;
253   loop invariant 0<= i <=len;
254   loop invariant \forall integer j; 0<=j< i ==> arr1[j] == arr2[j];
255   loop variant len-i; */
256   for (int i = 0; i < len; i++){
257     if (arr1[i] != arr2[i])
258       return 1; }
259   return 0;
260 }
261 #define NO_HASH_APP -1
262
263 /* For all hash stubs
264 Params: msg      : input message to hash
265        msg_sz    : input size
266        out_hash  : output for hash
267 Returns: hash size */
268
269 // Precondition using same_content checks that hash is applied on
270 // (entire) input message of pars_PKCS1_lev1 - in_msg. Property P5.

```

```

271 /*@
272   requires \valid_read(msg + (0 ..msg_sz-1));
273   requires msg_sz >= 0;
274   requires same_content(msg, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
275   requires g_backup_len == msg_sz;
276   requires g_hash_app == NO_HASH_APP;
277   terminates \true;
278   exits \false;
279   assigns out_hash[0 .. 31], g_hash_app;
280   ensures g_hash_app == SHA256_INDEX;
281   ensures \result == (int)32;
282 */
283 int stub_sha256(ul* msg, int msg_sz, ul* out_hash);
284
285 /*@
286   requires \valid_read(msg + (0 ..msg_sz-1));
287   requires msg_sz >= 0;
288   requires same_content(msg, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
289   requires g_backup_len == msg_sz;
290   terminates \true;
291   exits \false;
292   assigns out_hash[0 .. 63], g_hash_app;
293   ensures g_hash_app == SHA512_INDEX;
294   ensures \result == (int)64;
295 */
296 int stub_sha512(ul* msg, int msg_sz, ul* out_hash);
297
298 /*@
299   requires \valid_read(msg + (0 ..msg_sz-1));
300   requires msg_sz >= 0;
301   requires same_content(msg, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
302   requires g_backup_len == msg_sz;
303   terminates \true;
304   exits \false;
305   assigns out_hash[0 .. 19], g_hash_app;
306   ensures g_hash_app == SHA1_INDEX;
307   ensures \result == (int)20;
308 */
309 int stub_shal(ul* msg, int msg_sz, ul* out_hash);
310
311 /*Reads Tag and Length of next TLV
312 Params:  msg           : start of TLV sequence
313          OUTPUT:num_read: already consumed bytes of msg
314          num_to_read   : size of TLV sequence in bytes
315          exp_tag       : next expected Tag
316          OUTPUT:tlv_size: size of read TLV
317 Returns: ERR_LEN      : there is not enough space for next TLV
318          ERR_TAG      : if read Tag is not expected
319          0             : otherwise */
320 /*@
321   requires \valid_read(msg + (0 .. num_to_read - 1));
322   requires \valid(num_read);
323   requires \valid(tlv_size);
324   requires \separated(num_read, tlv_size, msg + (0 .. num_to_read - 1));
325   requires num_to_read >= 0;
326   requires 0 <= *num_read <= INT_MAX - 2;
327   assigns *num_read, *tlv_size;
328   ensures \result == 0 || \result == ERR_LEN || \result == ERR_TAG;
329   ensures \result == 0 ==> \old(*num_read) + LEN_TAGLEN <= num_to_read;
330   ensures \result == 0 ==> msg[\old(*num_read)] == exp_tag;
331   ensures \result == 0 ==> *num_read == \old(*num_read) + 2;
332   ensures \result == 0 ==> *tlv_size == msg[\old(*num_read) + 1];
333   ensures \result == ERR_LEN ==> \old(*num_read) + LEN_TAGLEN > num_to_read;
334   ensures \result == ERR_TAG ==> msg[\old(*num_read)] != exp_tag;
335 */
336 int read_one_tlv(ul* msg, int* num_read, int num_to_read, uint exp_tag,
337 int *tlv_size)
338 {

```

```

339 // there is enough place for TAG and LEN fields
340 if (*num_read + LEN_TAGLEN > num_to_read)
341 { return ERR_LEN; }
342
343 if(msg[(*num_read)++] != exp_tag)
344 { return ERR_TAG; }
345
346 *tlv_size = msg[(*num_read)++];
347 return 0; }
348
349 /* Parse TLV level 2 and 3,
350 i.e. DigestInfo and DigestAlgorithm Values
351 Params: dig_inf      : message to parse, DigestInfo Value
352         dig_inf_sz   : size of dig_inf
353         msg_to_hash  : message to hash
354         msg_sz       : size of msg_to_hash
355         expect_hash_ind: hash to be used for match
356 Returns: ERR_LEN     : there is not enough space for next TLV
357         ERR_TAG      : read Tag is not expected
358         ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST: sizes of parent and children TLVs are not
359         consistent
360         ERR_HASH_SZ  : parsed hash size does not match parsed hash
361         function
362         ERR_HASH_OID  : parsed hash function is not expected
363         ERR_NULL_SZ  : NULL TLV does not have 0 size
364         ERR_HASH_VAL  : recomputed hash does not match parsed hash
365         PASS_OK      : otherwise */
366 /*@
367 requires \valid(dig_inf + (0 .. dig_inf_sz-1));
368 requires 0<= dig_inf_sz <= INT_MAX;
369 requires \valid(msg_to_hash + (0 .. msg_sz-1));
370 requires 0<= msg_sz <= INT_MAX;
371 requires \separated(dig_inf + (0 ..), hash_res + (0 ..), hash_len_for_oid + (0..),
372   OID_list + (0..), SHA256_OID +(0 ..), SHA512_OID +(0 ..), SHA1_OID +(0 ..));
373
374 requires 0 <= expect_hash_ind < SUPP_OID_COUNT;
375
376 //check that we pass (entire) input message of pars_PKCSI_level
377 requires same_content(msg_to_hash, &g_backup_mes_to_hash[0], msg_sz);
378 requires g_backup_len == msg_sz;
379
380 requires g_hash_app == NO_HASH_APP;
381
382 assigns g_tlv_p[1][1], g_tlv_p[2][0..1], g_hash_app;
383 assigns hash_res[0..63];
384
385 ensures \result==ERR_LEN || \result==ERR_TAG || \result==ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST ||
386   \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ||
387   \result == ERR_HASH_VAL || \result == PASS_OK;
388
389 //SECURITY PART
390 behavior sec_format:
391   ensures format: \result == PASS_OK ==>
392     \exists integer prev_pars; valid_tlv(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz,
393     g_tlv_2[0], 1, \true);
394
395 behavior sec_prim_tlv:
396   ensures ghost_set: \result == PASS_OK ==>
397     \exists integer prev_pars; prim_gh_set(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz,
398     g_tlv_2[0], 1, \true);
399   ensures prim_tlv:(\result == PASS_OK) ==> prim_tlv(expect_hash_ind);
400
401 //COMPATIBILITY (ACCEPTANCE) PART
402 behavior acc_format:
403   ensures format: \result == ERR_LEN || \result == ERR_TAG ||
404     \result == ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST ==>
405     (!\exists integer prev_pars; valid_tlv(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz,
406     g_tlv_2[0], 1, \true));

```

```

407
408 behavior acc_prim_tlv:
409     ensures ghost_set: \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID ||
410         \result == ERR_HASH_VAL || \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==>
411         \exists integer prev_pars; prim_gh_set(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz,
412         g_tlv_2[0], 1, \true);
413     ensures prim_tlv: \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID ||
414         \result == ERR_HASH_VAL || \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==>
415         prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
416 */
417 int pars_PKCS1_lev2(ul* dig_inf, int dig_inf_sz, ul* msg_to_hash, int msg_sz,
418 uint expect_hash_ind)
419 {
420     // Parsing of TLV Level 2
421     // ===== LEVEL 2 =====
422
423     int seq_l2_len, off = 0;
424     int res = read_one_tlv(dig_inf, &off, dig_inf_sz, TAG_SEQ, &seq_l2_len);
425     if(res!=0) return res;
426
427     // Remember offset of OID's TAG field
428     int oid_off = off;
429
430     // Skip to OCTET_STRING TAG (contains hash) and store it into ghosts
431     off += seq_l2_len;
432     // Store pointer to primitive TLV inside ghost array
433     /*@ ghost g_tlv_p[1][1] = &dig_inf[off]; */
434     // To help instantiation of prim_gh_set
435     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv:
436     assert prim_tlv_stored(dig_inf, 2, 1, off); */
437
438     int hash_len;
439     res = read_one_tlv(dig_inf, &off, dig_inf_sz, TAG_OCT, &hash_len);
440     if(res!=0) return res;
441
442     // Remember offset of hash VALUE field
443     int hash_val_off = off;
444
445     //TLV LEVEL 2 nesting property
446     if (off + hash_len!= dig_inf_sz)
447     {
448         return ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST;
449     }
450
451     // If LEVEL 2 consistent, we continue to LEVEL 3
452     // ===== LEVEL 3 =====
453
454     ul* oid_start = &dig_inf[oid_off];
455     off = 0;
456
457     /*@ ghost g_tlv_p[2][0] = &oid_start[off]; */
458     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv:
459     assert prim_tlv_stored(oid_start, 1, 2, off);*/
460
461     int oid_len;
462     res = read_one_tlv(oid_start, &off, seq_l2_len, TAG_OID, &oid_len);
463     if(res!=0) return res;
464
465     int oid_val_off = off;
466     off += oid_len;
467
468     /*@ ghost g_tlv_p[2][1] = &oid_start[off]; */
469     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv:
470     assert prim_tlv_stored(oid_start, 2, 2, off); */
471
472     int null_size;
473     res = read_one_tlv(oid_start, &off, seq_l2_len, TAG_NULL, &null_size);
474     if(res!=0)

```

```

475     /*@ for acc_format: assert \forall integer prev_pars;
476     !valid_tlv(dig_inf,prev_pars,dig_inf_sz,g_tlv_2[0], 1,\true);*/
477     return res;
478
479     if(null_size + off != seq_l2_len)
480     {/*@ for acc_format: assert (\forall integer prev_pars;
481     !valid_tlv(dig_inf,prev_pars,dig_inf_sz,g_tlv_2[0], 1,\true));*/
482     return ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST;}
483
484     // Init inductive step for TLV level 2 and 3
485     // To confirm correct pointers setting if null_size is wrong
486     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv:
487     assert prim_gh_set(oid_start, 0, 0, 0, 2, \true); */
488     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv:
489     assert prim_gh_set(dig_inf, 0, 0, 0, 1, \true); */
490
491     if(null_size != 0)
492     return ERR_NULL_SZ;
493
494     // If TLV structure is OK, we continue to TLV content
495     // ===== PRIMITIVE TLVs CHECKS =====
496
497     if (oid_len == OID_list[expect_hash_ind][0] &&
498     !cmp_arr(&oid_start[oid_val_off], &OID_list[expect_hash_ind][1], oid_len))
499     {
500     if (hash_len != hash_len_for_oid[expect_hash_ind])
501     {
502     return ERR_HASH_SZ;
503     }
504
505     int hash_out_size = 0;
506     // Re-hash input message
507     switch(expect_hash_ind){
508     case SHA256_INDEX:
509     hash_out_size = stub_sha256(msg_to_hash, msg_sz, hash_res);
510     break;
511     case SHA512_INDEX:
512     hash_out_size = stub_sha512(msg_to_hash, msg_sz, hash_res);
513     break;
514     case SHA1_INDEX:
515     hash_out_size = stub_shal(msg_to_hash, msg_sz, hash_res);
516     break;
517     }
518
519     if(hash_out_size!= hash_len_for_oid[expect_hash_ind])
520     /*@ assert dead1: \false;
521     return ERR_INTER_BAD_CRYPT;
522
523     // Due to stub_shaX writing, we move valid_tlv and prim_gh_set
524     // initial steps here. For prim_gh_set we repeat the init.
525     /*@ for sec_format: //initial step for Level 2
526     assert valid_tlv(dig_inf, 0, 0, 0, 1, \true); */
527     /*@ for sec_format: //initial step for Level 3
528     assert valid_tlv(oid_start, 0, 0, 0, 2, \true); */
529     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv: //initial step for Level 2
530     assert prim_gh_set(oid_start, 0, 0, 0, 2, \true); */
531     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv: //initial step for Level 3
532     assert prim_gh_set(dig_inf, 0, 0, 0, 1, \true); */
533
534     // compare re-computed and parsed hashes
535     if (cmp_arr(&dig_inf[hash_val_off], hash_res, hash_out_size))
536     /*@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
537     /*@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert (\exists integer prev_pars;
538     prim_gh_set(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz, g_tlv_2[0],
539     1, \true)); */
540     return ERR_HASH_VAL;
541     else
542     // nominal case

```

```

543     return PASS_OK;
544 }
545 /*@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert (\exists integer prev_pars;
546   prim_gh_set(dig_inf,prev_pars,dig_inf_sz,g_tlv_2[0],1,\true));*/
547 /*@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
548   return ERR_HASH_OID;
549 */;
550
551 // prefix_prop      : 2 prefix bytes
552 // padding_prop     : sequence of 0xFF and delimiter
553 // asn_prop         : top level inductive predicate valid_tlv
554 // ghost_set_prop   : top level inductive predicate prim_gh_set
555 // Boundary between 0xFF padding and ASN.1
556 /*@ ghost_uint pad_bound;*/
557 /*@ predicate prefix_prop(ul* pad_msg) =
558   pad_msg[OFF_B1] == EXP_B1 && pad_msg[OFF_B2] == EXP_B2;
559 predicate padding_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound)=
560   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
561   (\forallall integer padd_off; 2 <= padd_off < pad_bound ==>
562     pad_msg[padd_off] == EXP_FF) && pad_msg[pad_bound] == EXP_DELIM;
563 predicate asn_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound,
564   integer tlv_num) =
565   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
566   \exists integer prev_pars; valid_tlv(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1, prev_pars,
567     pad_msg_sz - pad_bound - 1, tlv_num, 0, \true);
568 predicate ghost_set_prop(ul* pad_msg, integer pad_msg_sz, integer pad_bound,
569   integer tlv_num)=
570   2+ MIN_FF_COUNT <= pad_bound < pad_msg_sz &&
571   \exists integer prev_pars; prim_gh_set(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1, prev_pars,
572     pad_msg_sz - pad_bound -1, tlv_num, 0, \true); */
573
574 /*Parse prefix padding and TLV level 1
575 Params:  pad_msg      : message to parse, DigestInfo TLV
576          pad_msg_sz   : size of pad_msg
577          in_msg       : message to hash
578          in_msg_sz    : size of in_msg
579          expect_hash_ind: hash to be used for match
580 Returns: ERR_B1      : first byte has unexpected value
581          ERR_B2      : second byte has unexpected value
582          ERR_FF_COUNT : sequence of 0xFF bytes is shorter than 8
583          ERR_DELIM   : there is unexpected delimiter
584          ERR_LEN     : there is not enough space for next TLV
585          ERR_TAG     : read Tag is not expected
586          ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST: sizes of parent and children TLVs are not
587             consistent
588          ERR_HASH_SZ  : parsed hash size doesn't match parsed hash
589             function
590          ERR_HASH_OID : parsed hash function is not expected
591          ERR_NULL_SZ  : NULL TLV doesn't have 0 size
592          ERR_HASH_VAL : recomputed hash doesn't match parsed hash
593          PASS_OK     : otherwise */
594 /*@
595 requires \valid(pad_msg + (0 .. pad_msg_sz-1));
596 requires \valid(in_msg + (0 .. in_msg_sz - 1));
597 requires 0 <= expect_hash_ind < SUPP_OID_COUNT;
598 requires 0 <= pad_msg_sz <= INT_MAX- 255;
599 requires 0 <= in_msg_sz <= INT_MAX;
600 requires \separated(pad_msg + (0 ..), in_msg + (0 ..), hash_res + (0 ..),
601   hash_len_for_oid + (0..), OID_list + (0..), SHA256_OID +(0 ..),
602   SHA512_OID +(0 ..), SHA1_OID +(0 ..));
603
604 assigns pad_bound, g_tlv_p[0][0], g_tlv_p[1][0..1], g_tlv_p[2][0..1], g_hash_app,
605   g_backup_mes_to_hash[0 .. in_msg_sz-1];
606 assigns hash_res[0..63];
607
608 ensures \result == ERR_B1 || \result == ERR_B2 || \result == ERR_FF_COUNT ||
609   \result == ERR_DELIM || \result == ERR_LEN || \result == ERR_TAG ||
610   \result == ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST || \result == ERR_HASH_SZ ||

```

```

611  \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_NULL_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_VAL ||
612  \result == PASS_OK;
613
614 // ===== SECURITY PART =====
615 behavior sec_format:
616   ensures prefix: \result == PASS_OK ==> prefix_prop(pad_msg);
617   ensures pad: \result == PASS_OK ==>
618     padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound);
619   ensures asn: \result == PASS_OK ==>
620     asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
621
622 behavior sec_prim_tlv:
623   ensures ghost_set: \result == PASS_OK ==>
624     ghost_set_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
625   ensures prim_tlv: \result == PASS_OK ==> prim_tlv(expect_hash_ind);
626
627 // ===== COMPATIBILITY (ACCEPTANCE) PART =====
628 behavior acc_format:
629   ensures prefix:
630     \result == ERR_B1 || \result == ERR_B2 ==> !prefix_prop(pad_msg);
631   ensures pad:
632     \result == ERR_FF_COUNT || \result == ERR_DELIM ==>
633     \forall uint pad_bound; !padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound) ||
634     !asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
635   ensures asn:
636     \result == ERR_LEN || \result == ERR_TAG || \result == ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST ==>
637     \forall uint pad_bound; !padding_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound) ||
638     !asn_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
639
640 behavior acc_prim_tlv:
641   ensures ghost_set:
642     \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_HASH_VAL ||
643     \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==>
644     ghost_set_prop(pad_msg, pad_msg_sz, pad_bound, g_tlv_1[0]);
645   ensures prim_tlv:
646     \result == ERR_HASH_SZ || \result == ERR_HASH_OID || \result == ERR_HASH_VAL ||
647     \result == ERR_NULL_SZ ==> prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
648 */
649 int pars_PKCS1_level1(ul* pad_msg, int pad_msg_sz, ul* in_msg, int in_msg_sz,
650   uint expect_hash_ind)
651 {
652   //@ ghost g_make_backup(in_msg, in_msg_sz);
653   //@ ghost g_hash_app = NO_HASH_APP;
654
655   int dig_sz;
656   if(pad_msg_sz < 2)
657     return ERR_LEN;
658
659   int off = OFF_B1;
660   if (pad_msg[off++] != EXP_B1)
661     return ERR_B1;
662   if (pad_msg[off++] != EXP_B2)
663     return ERR_B2;
664
665   int ff_start = off;
666   /*@
667   loop assigns off;
668   loop invariant \at(off, LoopEntry) <= off <= pad_msg_sz;
669   loop invariant \forall integer i; (\at(off, LoopEntry) <= i < off) ==>
670     (pad_msg[i] == EXP_FF);
671   loop variant pad_msg_sz - off;
672   */
673   while ((off < pad_msg_sz) && (pad_msg[off] == EXP_FF))
674     off++;
675   if ((off - ff_start < MIN_FF_COUNT) || (off >= pad_msg_sz - 2))
676     { return ERR_FF_COUNT; }
677
678   if (pad_msg[off++] != EXP_DELIM)

```

```

679     return ERR_DELMIM;
680
681     // Store boundary between 0xFF padding and ASN.1
682     /*@ ghost pad_bound = off -1;*/
683
684     if (pad_msg[off++] != TAG_SEQ)
685         return ERR_TAG;
686
687     dig_siz = pad_msg[off++];
688
689     if (dig_siz + off != pad_msg_siz)
690         return ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST;
691
692     // Parse DigestInfo Value (TLV level 2 and 3)
693     int ret = pars_PKCS1_lev2(&pad_msg[off], dig_siz, in_msg, in_msg_siz,
694         expect_hash_ind);
695
696     // Initial inductive step for Level 1
697     /*@ assert valid_tlv(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, \true); */
698     // used for script for sec_asn (instantiation of inductive step)
699     /*@ for sec_format: assert
700     \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars,
701     integer tlv_num_pars, integer tlv_id, integer nest_prev_pars;
702     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
703     \let tlv_link = tlv_cur[OFF_LINK + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ];
704
705     ((1 <= tlv_num_pars) &&
706     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
707     ((ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == CONSTR) &&
708     valid_tlv(start + prev_pars + 2, nest_prev_pars, start[prev_pars + 1],
709     g_tlv_spec[tlv_link][OFF_COUNT], tlv_link, \true)
710     ) ==>
711     valid_tlv(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true);
712     */
713
714     // Initial inductive step for Level 1
715     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv: assert prim_gh_set(pad_msg + pad_bound + 1,
716     0, 0, 0, 0, \true); */
717     // used for script for sec_ghost_set, acc_ghost_set
718     // (instantiation of inductive step)
719     /*@ for sec_prim_tlv, acc_prim_tlv: assert
720     \forall ul* start, integer prev_pars, integer size_pars, integer tlv_num_pars,
721     integer tlv_id, integer nest_prev_pars;
722     \let tlv_cur = g_tlv_spec[tlv_id];
723     \let tlv_link = tlv_cur[OFF_LINK + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ];
724
725     ((1 <= tlv_num_pars) &&
726     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \false) &&
727     ((ul)tlv_cur[OFF_TYPE + (tlv_num_pars-1)*SPEC_ITEM_SZ] == CONSTR) &&
728     prim_gh_set(start + prev_pars + 2, nest_prev_pars, start[prev_pars + 1],
729     g_tlv_spec[tlv_link][OFF_COUNT], tlv_link, \true)
730     ) ==>
731     prim_gh_set(start, prev_pars, size_pars, tlv_num_pars, tlv_id, \true);
732     */
733
734     return ret;
735 }

```

A.2 Bug Detection Capability of the Proof

As explained in Sect. 5, we verify that if the parser accepts a padded message, it checks its every byte and ensures its uniqueness for every input message and hash function, according to [41]. This already gives a strong guarantee of absence

of a Bleichenbacher-like attack. However, to further strengthen trust in the correctness of our formal specification, we applied the proof on 4 parser variants (detailed in Sects. A.3–A.6), which break \mathcal{R}_{sec} and contain an exploitable bug. The resulting proof failures confirm that our specification cannot be proven for such buggy parsers. Since the specification can theoretically remain unproven for other reasons (such as a bug in the specification or a difficulty to perform automatic proof), we add a comment justifying why the failed clause is exactly the expected one. We used our parser and inserted bugs, which open the same kinds of *exploitable* vulnerabilities as the ones reported in the past on some established open source libraries. For the reader’s convenience, for each bug we show here an extract of the modified code with original code in comments.

Additionally, we tried to run the proof on 2 parser variants (detailed in Sects. A.7–A.8), which were modified to break $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$. The resulting proof failures confirm that our specification cannot be proven for such buggy parsers.

In the code extracts below, we clearly label if the parser variant violates \mathcal{R}_{sec} or $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ or both. The full code of the original parser can be found in Sect. A.1. The full code of all parser versions (the correct and the buggy ones) is part of the artifact.

A.3 \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug1: Ignored trailing bytes after the ASN.1 structure.

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig. 8.

```

684  if (pad_msg[off++] != TAG_SEQ)
685      return ERR_TAG;
686
687  dig_siz = pad_msg[off++];
688
689  //ORIGINAL:
690  //if (dig_siz + off != pad_msg_sz)
691  //BUGGY:
692  if (dig_siz + off > pad_msg_sz)
693      return ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST;
694
695  // Parse DigestInfo Value (TLV level 2 and 3)
696  int ret = pars_PKCS1_lev2(&pad_msg[off], dig_siz, in_msg, in_msg_sz,
697      expect_hash_ind);

```

Fig. 8: \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug1: the parser ignores trailing bytes after the ASN.1 structure.

We modify the check on the TLV at Level 1, which ensures the alignment of the ASN.1 structure with the end of the padded message. As a result, the parser ignores any byte stored after the ASN.1 end. It is the original vulnerability reported by Bleichenbacher [26].

Our specification is *not provable* for 3 ensures clauses of function `pars_PKCS1_lev1` (where the Level 1 TLV is handled). It is `asn` of `sec_format` behavior, and `ghost_set` of `sec_prim_tlv` and `acc_prim_tlv` behaviors. It is exactly the set of clauses which use inductive predicates `tlv_valid` and

`prim_gh_set` to express a correct message format. Notice that the modified check still ensures valid memory for the Level 2 and 3 TLV parsing (realized by `pars_PKCS1_lev2`) and does not affect its structural properties. Therefore, all RTE checks and contract of `pars_PKCS1_lev2` remain proven.

A.4 \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug2: Missing check of NULL TLV length (L_5).

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig.9.

```

473 res = read_one_tlv(oid_start, &off, seq_l2_len, TAG_NULL, &>null_size);
474 if(res!=0)
475     /*@ for acc_format: assert \forallinteger prev_pars;
476        !valid_tlv(dig_inf,prev_pars,dig_inf_sz,g_tlv_2[0], 1,\true);*/
477     return res;
478
479 if(null_size + off != seq_l2_len)
480     {/*@ for acc_format: assert (\forallinteger prev_pars;
481        !valid_tlv(dig_inf,prev_pars,dig_inf_sz,g_tlv_2[0], 1,\true));*/
482     return ERR_TLV_LEN_CONSIST;}
...
491 //ORIGINAL:
492 //if(null_size != 0)
493 //return ERR_NULL_SZ;
494 //BUGGY: (original code is removed)

```

Fig. 9: \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug2: Missing check of NULL TLV length (L_5).

The check for NULL TLV length (L_5) is skipped (see line 492). Although $\mathcal{P}_{\text{tree}}$ is checked on line 479, the content of NULL TLV value V_5 is ignored. It is the vulnerability reported in [36,43].

Our specification is not provable inside the `pars_PKCS1_lev2` function, more precisely, the `prim_tlv` ensures clause of `sec_prim_tlv` behavior. It is indeed the clause expressing the primitive TLVs content, including expected zero length of L_5 . Also we did check a correct message format, which explains why dedicated clauses remain proven.

A.5 \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug3: Ignored trailing bytes inside OID TLV (V_4).

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig.10.

The parsed OID V_4 and the expected OID (stored inside an internal array `OID_list`) are compared using the length of the latter (see lines 501–502). Next to that, the check of the parsed OID length L_4 is skipped (on line 498). As a result, if V_4 prefix matches the expected value, its remaining bytes are ignored. It is the vulnerability reported in [13].

Our specification is not provable for the same clause as for Bug2. Next to that, the bug is also detected by one supplementary annotation, i.e. a precondition of `cmp_arr`. Indeed, it is not guaranteed that the expected OID length used for comparison is not higher than L_4 . The rest of the justification is the same as for Bug2.

```

495 // ===== PRIMITIVE TLVs CHECKS =====
496
497 //ORIGINAL:
498 //if (oid_len == OID_list[expect_hash_ind][0] &&
499 //!cmp_arr(&oid_start[oid_val_off], &OID_list[expect_hash_ind][1], oid_len))
500 //BUGGY:
501 if (!cmp_arr(&oid_start[oid_val_off], &OID_list[expect_hash_ind][1],
502             OID_list[expect_hash_ind][0]))
503 {
504     if (hash_len != hash_len_for_oid(expect_hash_ind))
505     {
506         return ERR_HASH_SZ;
507     }

```

Fig. 10: \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug3: Ignored trailing bytes inside OID TLV (V_4).

A.6 \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug4: Ignored prefix padding bytes.

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig.11.

```

673 //ORIGINAL:
674 //while ((off < pad_msg_sz) && (pad_msg[off] == EXP_FF))
675 //BUGGY:
676 while ((off < pad_msg_sz) && (pad_msg[off] != EXP_DELIM))
677     off++;
678 if ((off - ff_start < MIN_FF_COUNT) || (off >= pad_msg_sz - 2))
679 { return ERR_FF_COUNT; }
680
681 if (pad_msg[off++] != EXP_DELIM)
682     return ERR_DELMIM;

```

Fig. 11: \mathcal{R}_{sec} violation—Bug4: Ignored prefix padding bytes.

The prefix padding is parsed by searching for the delimiter (byte 0x00), but without ensuring that only 0xFF bytes are present. As a result, any bytes except 0x00 are ignored inside the padding. It is the vulnerability reported in [50].

Our specification is not provable inside function `pars_PKCS1_lev1` for the contained loop invariant, which specifies the padding content. Next to that, this bug makes the branch on line 682 a dead code, with one corresponding failed smoke test. Some of \mathcal{R}_{sec} clauses are dependent on the loop invariant and remain conditionally proven.

A.7 $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ violation—Bug5: Restricted set of accepted hash functions.

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig.12.

On line 504, there is an additional condition, requiring the hash size to be at least 32 (excluding SHA-1).

Our specification is not provable inside function `pars_PKCS1_lev2`, more precisely, the `prim_tlv` ensures of `acc_prim_tlv` behavior. Indeed, if `expect_hash_ind` corresponds to SHA-1, the parser refuses the message even if it does not falsify a correct message content. Next to that, this bug makes unreachable the branch which re-computes SHA-1 over input message M, with two corresponding failed smoke tests.

```

500 //ORIGINAL:
501 //if (hash_len != hash_len_for_oid(expect_hash_ind))
502 //BUGGY:
503     if ((hash_len != hash_len_for_oid(expect_hash_ind)) ||
504         (hash_len < 32))
505     {
506         return ERR_HASH_SZ;
507     }

```

Fig. 12: $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ violation—Bug5: Restricted set of accepted hash functions.

A.8 \mathcal{R}_{sec} and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ violation—Bug6: Compare against a wrong hash value.

The relevant code extract is shown in Fig.13.

```

534 // compare re-computed and parsed hashes
535 //ORIGINAL:
536 //if (cmp_arr(&dig_inf[hash_val_off], hash_res, hash_out_size))
537 //BUGGY:
538     if (cmp_arr(&dig_inf[hash_val_off-1], hash_res, hash_out_size))
539 //@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert prim_tlv_neg(expect_hash_ind);
540 /*@ for acc_prim_tlv: assert (\exists integer prev_pars;
541     prim_gh_set(dig_inf, prev_pars, dig_inf_sz, g_tlv_2[0],
542     1, \true)); */
543     return ERR_HASH_VAL;
544 else
545     // nominal case
546     return PASS_OK;

```

Fig. 13: \mathcal{R}_{sec} and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ violation—Bug6: Compare against a wrong hash value.

Due to a shifted offset(see line 538), a wrong part of the padded message is compared against the re-computed hash value. (Comparison actually starts on $L3$ and not on $V3$). Because of this bug we accept a wrong value and refuse the correct one, and so both $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$ and \mathcal{R}_{sec} are not fulfilled. Note that this bug is not exploitable, mainly because it leaves only 1B (at the end of $V3$) ignored.

Our specification is not provable inside function `pars_PKCS1_lev2`. As expected, we cannot prove the clause expressing the correct hash value comparison. For \mathcal{R}_{sec} , it is the `prim_tlv` clause of the `sec_prim_tlv` behavior. For $\mathcal{R}_{\text{comp}}$, our specification is not proven for `assert` supporting verification of the clause `prim_tlv`, which is part of the `acc_prim_tlv` behavior.